

Angelo Leogrande^{1*o}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^oLUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Severe Material Deprivation in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2021

On average it decreased by 16.00% in the Italian regions

Istat calculates the serious material deprivation. Severe material deprivation is defined as the percentage of people in families who register at least four signs of material deprivation out of the nine listed below: i) not being able to bear unexpected expenses (of 850 euros starting from the 2020 survey); ii) not being able to afford a week's holiday away from home a year; iii) have arrears on the mortgage, rent, bills or other type of loan; iv) not being able to afford an adequate meal every two days, i.e. with meat or fish proteins (or vegetarian equivalent); v) not being able to adequately heat the home; not being able to afford: vi) a washing machine; vii) a color television; viii) a telephone; ix) a car. The available data refers to the period between 2004 and 2021 for the Italian regions. Only regions with a complete historical series were considered.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of severe material deprivation in 2021. Campania is in first place by value of severe material deprivation in 2021 with an amount of 17.3%, followed by Sicily with 9.6%, and Calabria with a value of 8.9%. In the middle of the table are the Marche with a value of 4.6%, followed by Piedmont with a value of 4.5%, and Basilicata with an amount of 4.3%. Umbria closes the ranking with a value of 2.00%, followed by Veneto with a value of 1.2% and Emilia Romagna with an amount of 0.8%.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in severe material deprivation between 2004 and 2021. Abruzzo is in first place in terms of value of severe material deprivation between 2004 and 2021 with a value of 157.14% equal to a change from an amount of 2.8% in 2004 up to a value of 7.2% in 2021 corresponding to a variation of 4.4 units. Liguria with a variation equal to 46.43% equal to a variation from an amount of 2.8% in 2004 up to a value of 4.1% equal to an amount of 1.3 units. In third place Piedmont with a variation corresponding to a variation of 32.35% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.4% in 2004 up to a value of 4.5% in 2021 or equal to a variation of 1, 1 unit. In the middle of the table are Tuscany with a variation equal to 4.00% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 2.5% in 2004 up to a value of 2.6% in 2021 corresponding to a variation of 0.1 unit. Campania follows with a variation of -1.14% as a variation corresponding to a variation from 17.5% in 2004 up to a value of 17.3% in 2021 or equal to a variation of -0.2% units. In tenth place is Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation of -34.38% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.2% in 2004 up to a value of 2.1% in 2021 or equal to a variation of - 1.1 units. Sicily closes the ranking with a variation of -41.82% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 16.5% in 2004 up to a value of 9.6% in 2021 or equal to a variation of -6.9 units . Emilia Romagna follows with a variation of -63.64% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 2.2% in 2004 up to a value of 0.8% in 2021 equal to -1.4 units. Veneto closes the ranking with a variation of -64.17%

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it , Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.4% in 2004 up to 1.2% in 2021 equal to a value of -2.2 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- *Cluster 1:* Puglia, Sicily, Campania, Calabria, Basilicata;
- *Cluster 2:* Friuli Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Piedmont, Umbria, Liguria, Veneto, Marche, Lazio, Abruzzo, Sardinia.

From the point of view of the average of the clusters it appears that the following ordering is: $C1 > C2$. That is, the value of material deprivation within the southern regions tends to be significantly higher than in the central-northern regions. Abruzzo is the only southern region to be included in cluster 2, i.e. the only southern region to have a level of material deprivation in line with the northern regions.

Severe material deprivation in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. The value of material deprivation in Northern Italy decreased by 14.29%, going from an amount of 2.8% in 2004 to a value of 2.4 % in 2021 or a change equal to an amount of -0.40 units. The value of material deprivation in the North-West grew by 22.22%, equal to a change from an amount of 2.7% in 2004 to 3.3% in 2021, or equal to a change of 0.60 units. Severe material deprivation in the North-East decreased by 60.71% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 2.8% in 2004 to 1.1% in 2021 or equal to a variation of -1.70 units. Severe material deprivation in Central Italy grew by 13.16% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.8% in 2004 to a value of 4.3% in 2021 or equal to a variation of 0.50 units. Severe material deprivation in the South decreased by 22.86%, going from a variation of 14.00% to a value of 10.8% corresponding to a variation of -3.20 units. Severe material deprivation in Southern Italy decreased by 16.31% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 14.1% in 2004 to a value of 11.8% in 2021 or corresponding to a variation of -2.30 units. Severe material deprivation decreased by 36.96% between 2004 and 2021, i.e. from an amount of 13.8% in 2004 to a value of 8.7% in 2021 corresponding to a variation of -5.10 units.

Conclusions. Severe material deprivation decreased between 2004 and 2021. However, if we look at the development of the historical series, calculated as the average of the Italian regions, we can note that the value of severe material deprivation remained more or less constant between 2004 and 2010 with a marginal growth from 6.45% up to 7.09%. However, between 2010 and 2011, in correspondence with the economic manifestation of the "Great Financial Crisis", there was an increase in serious material deprivation from an amount of 7.09% up to a value of 11.84%. Subsequently the value grew further to reach an amount of 14.05%. That is, between 2010 and 2012 the value of severe material deprivation doubled. Subsequently, the same value decreased until reaching a maximum minimum of the historical series equal to 2021 units or equal to 5.41%. Therefore, we can indicate the following propositions:

- The value of severe material deprivation decreased on average in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2021 by 16.00%;
- Severe material deprivation in Southern Italy is 4.50 times higher than in the North, 3.27% in the North-West, 9.82% in the North-East and 2.51% times higher in the Centre;
- During the economic manifestation of the "*Great Financial Crisis*", i.e. between 2010 and 2012, the value of severe material deprivation doubled on average in the Italian regions;
- Abruzzo is the only southern region to have a level of serious material deprivation comparable with the central-northern regions.

In any case, in Italy on average severe material deprivation affects around 5.6% of the population. Since the Italian population in 2021 was approximately 59 million people, it follows that approximately 3.3 million Italians suffer from serious material deprivation. In addition, of these, most live in the southern regions.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Leogrande, A., Birardi, G., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2019). Italian Universities: Institutional Mandate and Communitarian Engagement. *European Journal of Educational Management*, 2(2), 85-110.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. A Data-Driven Analysis.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The smes innovation in europe. Available at SSRN 3964059.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. Available at SSRN 4032975.

Laureti, Lucio, Alberto Costantiello, and Angelo Leogrando. "THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT." IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics. 2021.

Leogrando, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. Available at SSRN 4434206.

Appendix

Macro-Regioni	2004	2021	Var Ass	Var Per
Nord	2,8	2,4	-0,40	-14,29
Nord-ovest	2,7	3,3	0,60	22,22
Nord-est	2,8	1,1	-1,70	-60,71
Centro	3,8	4,3	0,50	13,16
Mezzogiorno	14	10,8	-3,20	-22,86
Sud	14,1	11,8	-2,30	-16,31
Isole	13,8	8,7	-5,10	-36,96

Grave Deprivazione Materiale		
Rank	Regione	2021
1	Campania	17,3
2	Sicilia	9,6
3	Calabria	8,9
4	Puglia	8,6
5	Abruzzo	7,2
6	Sardegna	6
7	Lazio	5,5
8	Marche	4,6
9	Piemonte	4,5
10	Basilicata	4,3
11	Liguria	4,1
12	Lombardia	2,7
13	Toscana	2,6
14	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	2,1
15	Umbria	2
16	Veneto	1,2
17	Emilia-Romagna	0,8

Grave Deprivazione Materiale nelle Regioni Italiane tra il 2004 ed il 2021									
Regione	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
Piemonte	3,4	2,2	4,2	4,6	3,3	5,7	4,7	7,8	7,3
Liguria	2,8	3,6	3,4	2,3	3,5	1,7	2,7	6,8	8,6
Lombardia	2,4	2,3	2,3	3	3,1	4,7	3,2	6,3	10,5
Veneto	3,4	3	3,2	3,4	2,9	3,9	4,1	4,1	4,2
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	3,2	2,9	3,8	4,1	3,8	4	2,5	6,5	6,4

Emilia-Romagna	2,2	3,1	2,4	3,3	3,2	3,5	4,2	6,6	7,3
Toscana	2,5	2,7	3,2	3,8	3,9	3,8	5,1	7,8	9,3
Umbria	3,4	3,8	2,5	2,7	3,2	4,3	4,1	5,7	10
Marche	4	3,6	4,8	4,4	4	4	4,9	10,6	10,5
Lazio	4,6	3,9	3,6	5,8	6,2	6,1	6,2	6,2	10,6
Abruzzo	2,8	5	3,9	5,3	4,9	4,9	5,4	13,2	8,1
Campania	17,5	15,5	14,5	14,3	16,6	12,2	13,9	18,3	21,8
Puglia	14,1	11,1	12,8	12,8	14,8	11,9	11,5	20,4	34
Basilicata	6,9	9,2	7,4	7,7	11,7	10,3	9,3	24,3	23,5
Calabria	14,6	15,8	10,8	12	10	10,7	11,6	20,9	22,2
Sicilia	16,5	18,3	15,2	16,7	18	18,5	19,5	25,7	35,9
Sardegna	5,4	10,5	10	8,5	12,4	10,5	7,6	10	8,7
Regione	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Piemonte	5	5,3	6,6	10,2	9	4,2	3,1	4,4	4,5
Liguria	8,1	12,7	11,6	7,9	8,6	4,4	3	4,7	4,1
Lombardia	9,2	8,5	6,4	6,1	6,4	3,1	4,7	3,9	2,7
Veneto	3,8	4,7	3,6	5	4,1	3,6	1,7	2	1,2
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	6,6	7,2	4,9	6,5	6	3,6	4,1	3,7	2,1
Emilia-Romagna	8,9	7,3	5,9	6,3	5,9	2,9	4	1,3	0,8
Toscana	4,8	7,3	8,9	7	6,8	5,3	3,4	2,2	2,6
Umbria	8,6	5,2	10,4	8,5	6,1	4,2	1,8	3,7	2
Marche	9,4	9,5	10,8	9,4	11	4,8	4	4,8	4,6
Lazio	7,1	7,3	7,2	9,5	8	7,8	7,8	7,1	5,5
Abruzzo	8,6	9,5	11,1	15,1	15,6	11,3	6,2	6,1	7,2
Campania	21,9	18,7	16,3	25,9	18,6	20,2	16,6	14	17,3
Puglia	24,7	23,2	26,9	19,8	15,1	12,8	11,9	10,4	8,6
Basilicata	20,7	15,1	14	14	8,4	12,2	8,8	5,4	4,3
Calabria	19,7	15,6	15,7	16	13,9	15,3	8,6	9,1	8,9
Sicilia	28,9	26	27,3	26,1	20,3	20,9	17,8	9,5	9,6
Sardegna	13,6	14,7	14,5	9,5	9	10,3	8	5,1	6

